

Grant agreement no. 312788

**ORCID AND DATAcite
INTEROPERABILITY NETWORK**

<http://odin-project.eu>

D2.4 Final communication report including results from final event

WP2 – Communication

V1_1

Final

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	D2.4 Final communication report including results from final event		
	WP2 Communication		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: J.Brown (ORCID), S.Dallmeier-Tiessen, L. Rueda (CERN), R.Kotarski, S.Ruiz (BL), T.Vision (Dryad)	Version: 1_1 Final	2/59

Abstract: Communication and community engagement is a central component of the ODIN project's goals. It facilitates the integration of persistent identifiers in current workflows and sets up the conditions required for a full adoption among the communities. This document describes ODIN's actions and achievements regarding communication and outreach.

This is an updated version of the interim report, which was submitted in August 2104. This version includes the results of the final event and other communications actions undertaken during September 2014.

Lead beneficiary: ORCID

Date: 20/10/2014

Nature: Report

Dissemination level: PU (Public)

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Introduction

Community engagement and outreach is a central component in the achievement of the ODIN project goals, and in the realisation of the project strategy. To support this activity, the project delivered three major events during its lifetime:

- Kick-off Meeting (Berlin, October 2012),
- First Year Event and Codesprint (Geneva, October 2013)
- Project Final Event (Amsterdam, September 2014).

The content and impact of each event is discussed in detail in Chapter 5. Each one reflected the maturation of the project over time. The first was very much a 'scene-setting' exercise. The second, the first-year event, was more of a 'listening' exercise, divided between presentations of the project's activities, invited presentations and feedback from the community. The third, the project's final event, took stock of the project's achievements and lessons, and drew together a community of experts to discuss how to build on the ODIN legacy.

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The communication activities spanned the two years of the project. Year one focused on raising awareness of the project and promoting the initial findings and deliverables emerging from the team's activities. In year two, incorporating constructive suggestions emerging from the first year review, the team directed communication activities into a broad range of focused community interventions, targeting sub-sections of the broader ODIN audience to ensure that the core messages and value delivered by the project were understood fully by each stakeholder group. A detailed communication action plan (ODIN Dissemination and Community Engagement Action Plan, May 2014) was developed specifically to maximise the impact of activities during the final months of the project; this has generated very high levels of interest and engagement.

A range of materials have been presented, including:

- High level how-to guides aimed at communities of practice (librarians, funders etc.)
- informal sessions with groups of researchers to raise awareness of the importance/potential usefulness of data and person identifiers
- topic-driven conference presentations and articles (members of the project have produced 13 formal conference papers during the life of the project)
- a range of online and new media interactions (ODIN website, twitter feed, webinars, blogs, and other social media).

The ODIN approach and findings have been embedded into the broader field of practice evolving around Persistent Identifier (PID) implementation and services, research data infrastructures and policies, and international initiatives to deliver the potential benefits of modern e-infrastructures to the widest possible range of research stakeholders. This has been achieved by numerous strategic engagements with groups

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active in the field or in related endeavours, from Research Data Alliance working groups to access and identity management.

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Creation and Dissemination of Derived Materials

The majority of ODIN's dissemination efforts during its first year were developed as general outreach actions. Although these sorts of documents (technical reports, publications and presentations) provided a good overview of the project, during the second year the focus shifted to be more specific and community oriented.

At the beginning of the year, the project partners started generating stakeholder related materials, as well as general dissemination material, so the different user communities are provided with practical, accessible and tailor-made usable inputs. Such materials have been published using a renewed and more efficient project website.

As well as these publications, the project members have been blogging and using social media to promote ODIN activities and outputs, and there have been a number of concrete outreach activities, such as webinars.

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Jon Tennant @Protohedgehog · 15 May 2013

Ooh, another cool addition from @ORCID_Org - worth checking out academy types! bit.ly/19sblLd

RETWEET
1

FAVORITE
1

4:24 AM - 15 May 2013 · Details

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Martin Fenner @mfenner · 15 May 2013

@Protohedgehog ORCID/DataCite integration tool at datacite.labs.orcid-eu.org allows you to import all your @figshare content into ORCID registry

Expand ↩ Reply ↻ Retweet ★ Favorite ⋮ More

Jon Tennant @Protohedgehog · 15 May 2013

.@mfenner @figshare Just did it, loved it, told everyone nearby to do it! Also added ORCID profile to the top of my CV :)

Expand ↩ Reply ↻ Retweet ★ Favorite ⋮ More

By deploying a mix of targeted (stakeholder or topic specific, e.g. webinars, how-to guides) and broad interest (general updates, new announcements, e.g. blog posts) communications, the project team have ensured that stakeholder groups and communities of practice that have a clear interest in the area of PIDs (such as repository managers, data managers etc.) hear directly from the project and are abreast of the latest developments. At the same time, we have sought to maximise serendipitous discovery of our work by continuing to broadcast more general updates about activities and outputs.

This chapter sets out a comprehensive view of the content and materials generated from the project, beyond the core deliverables, and the ways that the team have

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packaged project findings, updates and developments for a range of media. These materials are broken down into broad categories for the sake of simplicity: website, training materials, codesprints and hackathons, blogposts, social media, webinars and printed material.

Website

The project website was re-designed in April 2014 (See Fig. 1) with the twin aims of providing a more intuitive and modern user experience and in providing a better platform for the growing quantity of project information and outputs.

Fig. 1: The redesigned ODIN website.

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The original design style was maintained but a more extensive and better-organised structure was developed. Further information about ODIN, its members and actions is provided on the website and the resources generated by the project have a specific section, where such material is published, organised and linkable. The same approach has been used for conferences, events, papers and blog posts. Each of these is discussed in more detail in dedicated sections below.

The website is now a much more effective hub for information about the project, and contains a rich mix of resources and media.

Training materials

As noted above, one of the main drivers for the redesign of the project website was the creation of an easy-to-navigate platform to house both the formal project deliverables and re-packaged and synthesised material. A key component is a series of short, efficient training guides, explaining the core concepts and findings of the project (see Fig. 2). The guides have been presented in several different ways, including by type (ranging from introductory materials to varied analyses) and stakeholder group (publishers, librarians etc.). The effect of this approach is to ensure that key target groups can swiftly access information that is specific to them, and that anyone looking for general, beginners' guides can easily filter out detailed material, simplifying their access to explanatory information about the project.

As the final deliverables, especially from Work Packages 3 and 5, were completed in the final weeks and months of the project, an extended and updated suite of derived materials was added to the project website. These take the form of specifications,

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guidelines, processes and checklists to help implementers and service users to benefit from the ODIN project findings and experience.

An 8-page project findings document (see fig. 3), has also been made available electronically via the site. Additionally, printed copies of this booklet were shared with delegates at the 4th RDA Plenary in Amsterdam and at the project final event in September 2014. A stock of printed copies of this booklet has been shared with all the project partners to be distributed to audiences at relevant events in the coming months.

ODIN E-INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS ACTIONS

ACTIONS	BENEFICIARIES
(1) Lower access barriers for institutions to participate to interoperable global PID infrastructures, through appropriate agreements between institutions, fostering collaborations and with the support of national/international bodies.	E-INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS, LINKING RESEARCH INSTIT.
(2) Support scientific communities without existing PID solutions to participate to existing interoperable PID frameworks, while tailoring interfaces to their specificity.	RESEARCH COMMUNITIES
(3) Facilitate interoperability between stakeholders with community-specific, institution specific or national PID solutions and emerging global open solutions.	E-INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS, RESEARCH COMMUNITIES, FUNDING AND POLICYMAKERS
(4) Develop an interoperable PID infrastructure that supports development of third-party tools for discoverability, impact assessment, and other value added services.	RESEARCH COMMUNITIES, FUNDING AND POLICYMAKERS
(5) Design policies to evaluate data to a key indicator in research assessment, with appropriate attribution to their creators and curators, through open and interoperable PIDs.	RESEARCH COMMUNITIES
(6) Harmonize formats and APIs, so that information from emerging and existing PID frameworks can be exposed and mutually enriched, while enabling third-party discovery services.	RESEARCH COMMUNITIES, FUNDING AND POLICYMAKERS
(7) Assure that a trusted/open/sustainable/interoperable PID infrastructure is established with ease of participation of 3rd parties.	E-INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS
(8) Establish a participative framework with PIDs for contributions and materials, where any participant can expose information, enriching the entire infrastructure.	RESEARCH COMMUNITIES, FUNDING AND POLICYMAKERS

The project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no. 312736.

ODIN TRUSTED IDENTIFIERS are...

unique, governed, persistent, interoperable, descriptive

Trusted identifiers have the following characteristics:

- are **unique on a global scale**, allowing large numbers of unique identifiers
- resolve as HTTP URIs **persistently** with support for **content negotiation**
- come with **metadata** that describe their most relevant properties, including a minimum set of **common metadata elements**
- a **search** of metadata elements across all trusted identifiers of that service should be possible
- are **interoperable with other identifiers** through metadata elements that describe their relationship
- are **issued and managed by an organization** that focuses on that goal as its primary mission, has a sustainable business model and a **critical mass** of member organizations, agreed common procedures and policies, governing body, and is committed to using **open technologies**

Based on the Den Haag Manifesto

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Fig. 2: One page training guides for general dissemination.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Lower access barriers for participation to interoperable global PID e-Infrastructures
Acting

Broaden the scope of PID solutions to address needs of the "long tail", less data-intensive, sciences and support their participation
Acting

Facilitate interoperability between community- and/or institution-specific or national PID solutions through global open solutions
Acting

Provide funding to ease local access, integration and participation in emerging PID infrastructures
Acting

Provide documentation and technical specifications for the implementation of PID infrastructures that supports development of third-party tools for discoverability, impact assessment, and other value added services
Acting

Generic scientific data workflows:


```

graph TD
    Producer[Producer] --> DataDeposit[Data deposit]
    DataDeposit --> Ingest[ingest]
    Ingest --> Archiving[Archiving]
    Archiving --> Dissemination[Dissemination and access]
    Dissemination --> Reuse[Reuse]
    Reuse --> Consumer[Consumer]

    ORCID1[ORCID] -- ORCID --> DataDeposit
    DataCite1[DataCite] -- Metadata ORCID --> Ingest
    DataCite1 -- DOI --> Ingest
    ORCID2[ORCID Claim Process] -.-> Ingest
    ORCID2 -.-> Archiving
    DataCite2[DataCite] -- Metadata ORCID --> Dissemination
    DataCite2 -- DOI --> Dissemination

    subgraph AIP_SIP [AIP/SIP]
        DataDeposit
        Ingest
    end

    subgraph DIP [DIP]
        Reuse
    end

    subgraph Process_Include [Process include]
        P1[Data creation]
        P2[Metadata creation]
        P3[Metadata processing]
        P4[Documentation]
        P5[Name validation]
        P6[Quality assurance]
        P7[Curator]
        P8[Preservation formatting]
        P9[Dissemination formatting]
        P10[Indexing]
    end

```

Fig. 3 : Pages from the "project findings" booklet.

Codesprints

The ODIN team participated in, organised and sponsored three codesprints during the project. These generated a great deal of developer interest and drove the development of eight ODIN-linked projects.

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ORCID Outreach meeting Hackathon

At the ORCID Outreach Meeting¹, in Oxford, UK, in May 2013, members of the ODIN team participated in the ORCID Hackathon creating a set of tools for search and claim workflows, refining and extending the existing DataCite “search & claim” tool by linking it to other works catalogues.

Open Science @openscience · 16 May 2013
 New data citation tool integrated with @ORCID_Org: buff.ly/14pZ5d9 @mfenner & @gthorisson forking code by @CrossRefNews #openscience

RETWEETS **4** FAVORITES **7**

3:43 AM - 16 May 2013 · Details

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ODIN First Year Event Codesprint

At the ODIN first year event, hosted at CERN, in Geneva, Switzerland, 20 developers came together in the ODIN codesprint and worked on four projects. Participants came from both ODIN partners and from external organizations not directly involved in ODIN. Among the external experts were Roy Boverhof (Server.biz) and Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltrán (University of Oxford), who won the best project competition at the

¹ <https://orcid.org/orcid-outreach-meeting-symposium-and-codefest-may-2013>

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ORCID Codefest held at Oxford on May 6 2013 and were funded to attend the ODIN event in Geneva. Summaries of the projects are reproduced here.

Embedding all my ORCID-claimed works (including data) on a webpage

This project built on previous work by ORCID EU Labs to create a set of simple tools for ORCID users to easily embed a list of their claimed works in a personal web page. On the server side, the ORCID Feed service, originally created by Martin Fenner, retrieves a list of works from the ORCID API and transforms it into a feed of items in a variety of formats and citation styles. This tool was extended to support a companion client side JavaScript code which fetches a formatted citation feed and inserts into the user's web page as a bibliography. The user only needs to add one line of JavaScript and one line of CSS.

ODIN's HAMR – Human/Authority Metadata Reconciliation

This project grew from the need for a data centre to add ORCIDs for creators of works in their own system (and push this information to DataCite) as researchers claim their works via the ORCID system.

The service developed that allows a set of DOIs to be registered and monitored for changes of authorship within ORCID. The authorship information will be intelligently "diffed" against the DOI metadata and differences provided to the registrant. This could either be as a batch job, a query API or a human readable website.

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The example used for this project was the Dryad data repository, where less than 10 authors had included their ORCID in works metadata before. Using HAMR, around 500 instances were discovered, where more than 300 were unique.

ORCID Union for data

A common challenge for all stakeholders is the integration of metadata describing persons and works stored in various unconnected systems or “silos”. The goal of this project was to enable person lookup in OKKAM’s Entity Name System (ENS)² based on metadata harvested from DataCite and the ORCID public data dump. The tool can be used to “de-silo” links between an ORCID and a person’s works across multiple sources.

DataCite metadata form with ORCID lookup

Looking up ORCID identifiers by name is a common requirement for ORCID integrators. This project implemented ORCID lookup for DataCite as an HTML form, using a widget that can be reused by others.

Full details of all of these projects, with links to the source code are available from the project website³.

² <http://www.okkam.org/>

³ <http://odin-project.eu/project-outputs/first-codesprint-oct-2013/>

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Open Repositories 2014 Developer Challenge

ODIN co-sponsored the Open Repositories 2014 (OR14)⁴ Developer Challenge. Of 10 projects entered into the challenge, three were focused on engagement with PIDs (ORCID iDs and DataCite DOIs).

Data Cite - ORCID Refresh

When a third-party does not have a resource anymore (deleted, moved), ORCID's repository should be updated. This tool refreshes the record.

The original version of this application was developed using Ruby, but it was not generic enough for reuse and deployment. The changes included during the codesprint included the replacement of hard-coded values, environment configuration, etc. It was also documented and deployed during the event.

Fill My List

Fill My List used the ORCID API as their starting point for PID implementation and then built out from that to abstract their PID integration in the prototype for other PIDs. In Fill My List's view, IDs are useful, as researchers/data creators and so on will not always add verified information to IRs; they set out to automate the process using authority services. The team developed a repositories and authorities broker for classes of data from various sources: the idea being to optimize it once for the whole community.

⁴ <http://or2014.helsinki.fi/>

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They also created an abstract form for each class of data with a plugin for data for explicit repository platforms.

ORCID & Sufia

Sufia is a Rails engine for creating a self-deposit institutional repository, including ingest, curation, and search of digital resources. It is buildt on the Hydra Framework.

This was an exploratory project to investigate the introduction of ORCID support for Sufia. As it is a simple prebuilt system, its community would appreciate its simplicity and ease of maintenance, including ORCID iDs, pulling information, etc. The project continues in an early stage, the background functionality was implemented during the developer challenge, but the visualization and interface is still under development.

Further details about the projects as well as access to their source code, are provided in the OR14's Developer Challenge website⁵.

Blog posts - ODIN and elsewhere

ODIN partners have blogged extensively about the project, both on the ODIN site, which has a dedicated section for the blog and on the sites of their home institutions.

At the time of writing, 19 blog posts have been added to the ODIN blog, promoting tools, project events, publications and new developments in the partnership (see Fig.

⁵ <http://or2014.helsinki.fi/?p=966>

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4). These have also been used to evolve best practice in data citation and promote collaborations with, for example, the Research Data Alliance.

The screenshot shows a blog post on the ODIN website. At the top is a blue navigation bar with links: Home, The ODIN mission, Blog, Events, Output and material, Project workplan, Partners, and Contact. The main content area has a title 'ORCID and DataCite sign an MoU' and a sub-header 'Posted on July 21, 2014 by Laura Rueda'. The text of the post reads: 'Thanks to the ODIN collaboration, bonds are being strengthened. ORCID and DataCite are pleased to announce their joint commitment to research data by signing a Memorandum of Understanding. ORCID and DataCite agree that data are essential building blocks of scholarship and research in the sciences, medicine, social sciences, and humanities. Researchers and scholars recognize the potential for increasing collaboration and synthesis when data are archived, published, and shared, forging the possibility for new discoveries built upon prior work. This vision requires that data be discoverable, citable, and connected to the people who created it. Reliable persistent data and researcher identification are essential to establish these links. The two organizations are working together to improve and harmonize DataCite and ORCID metadata schemas for data and researchers, to develop new interoperable and open source APIs for our services, and to create complementary user services.' To the right of the text is a vertical sidebar with a blue header 'ODIN project, ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network', a large ODIN logo, and a 'Recent Posts' section.

Fig. 4: Screenshot of a post on the ODIN blog.

This key promotional activity has been reinforced heavily by the project partners. The ORCID blog has featured ODIN in 10 posts (see Fig. 5) and the DataCite blog has featured ODIN in 5 posts (see Fig. 6). Posts have primarily focussed on promoting project milestones, events and tools, although posts from the ORCID blog also refer to ODIN in discussions of the state-of-the-art.

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ANDS have also promoted ODIN in 2 articles in their newsletter (see Fig. 7).

ORCID
Connecting Research and Researchers

FOR RESEARCHERS FOR ORGANIZATIONS ABOUT HELP SIGN IN

Submitted by Rebecca Bryant on Tue, 07/30/2013 - 20:57

ORCID has three events coming up in September and October, to provide the research community opportunities to learn more about integration of ORCID identifiers, and to participate in developing best practice recommendations.

19 September 2013. ORCID iDs in the Academic Publishing Workflow: Where are we now?

Join us for a Webinar on Thursday, September 19 at 11:00 EDT, co-hosted by ORCID and CrossRef. This webinar will include discussion and demonstrations of the integration of ORCID identifiers in publishing workflows, including manuscript submission, production and online publication, and XML deposit to CrossRef.

Participation is free, though advance registration is required. [Register Now.](#)

15-17 October 2013. ODIN First Year Conference and Codesprint.

The ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network (ODIN) project, which we covered previously on our blog, will

Fig. 5: Screenshot of a post on the ORCID blog promoting ODIN.

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Helping you to find,
access, and reuse data

Home

ODIN project webinar video now available
Published by Jan Brase on 5 June 2014 - 1:25pm

Thank you all for registering for the ODIN project data webinar, which was held June 3rd and attracted up to 160 people.

We are pleased to inform you that videos and slides from the webinar are now available from the ODIN project site, at:

<http://odin-project.eu/events/webinars/>

If you have any questions for the presenters, please do not hesitate to contact us via the ODIN project email address:

info@odin-project.eu

Why cite data?

What is DataCite?

What do we do?

Fig. 6: Screenshot of a post on the DataCite blog promoting ODIN.

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The European connection

Amir Aryani, ANDS

ANDS is at work in Europe as a co-partner on a European Commission-funded e-infrastructure project.

Since September 2012, ANDS has been a partner of the ODIN project alongside CERN, the British Library, ORCID, DataCite, Dryad and arXiv.

ODIN (ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network) is aiming to build on the success of DataCite and ORCID to provide author and object identifiers.

The DataCite consortium (of which ANDS is a partner) has minted more than one million Digital Object Identifiers in the last few years, and ORCID is partnered with more than 280 organisations across 40 countries to provide a persistent connection between researchers and their research outcomes.

ODIN, set for completion at the end of this year, plans to address four primary challenges in enabling identity awareness: access, discovery, interoperability and sustainability.

ANDS is testing and providing international feedback on the ODIN interoperability model. This is being made tangible through the interoperability of services between ANDS' Research Data Australia (researchdata.ands.org.au), ORCID and DataCite.

ANDS has a working relationship with the National Library of Australia, Australian funding organisations and research institutions in establishing infrastructure to support public identifiers for researchers and research projects. ANDS is leveraging this experience in its work with ODIN.

See the article on page 6 about ORCID.

Fig. 7: Article in the ANDS Newsletter from April 2014 (issue 18) promoting ODIN.

Webinars

The project partners presented two webinars in 2014. The first, in June, was a technically-focussed webinar, exploring the data, APIs and implementations available from the project teams, and to encourage implementers from across the community to explore the possibilities offered by the ODIN approach to interoperability. The second webinar, held in September, explored the issue of PID interoperation from a policy perspective, focussing on community responses to the ODIN Roadmap.

The first webinar showcased the tools and innovations emerging from the project's technical developments. These tools build on the ORCID and DataCite PID infrastructures, and the webinar was designed as an opportunity for any developers

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interested in working with ORCID, DataCite or other organizations assigning PIDs to learn about the data available, to gain insight into the latest tools and services being built upon that data and to ask questions of the project team. In contrast to the audiences at many of the conferences the team have presented at, the webinar was aimed at those responsible for implementing ODIN's recommendations, and provided these technical staff with an opportunity to talk directly to the developers of ORCID and DataCite tools. Demonstrations and presentations were provided by Josh Brown and Laura Paglione (ORCID), Sebastian Peters (DataCite) and Laura Rueda (CERN).

There was a high demand from those who were unable to attend for access to recordings of the webinar, so each webinar presentation was recorded and made available via the dedicated webinar section on the ODIN website to enable those unable to attend due to other commitments or due to time zone differences to benefit from the sessions (see Fig. 8).

The second webinar, entitled "After ODIN: looking to the future" was designed to promote the findings of WP4 and WP5, both of which surveyed the current landscape of PID use and implementation. It offered a detailed discussion of the short- to medium-term steps to be taken to build upon the work done by ODIN, extend the usage and availability of PID services, and enable PID services and tools to evolve and grow. The lens for this discussion was the ODIN roadmap, and the emphasis was on policy makers, as distinct from the technical audience targeted in the first webinar.

The core concept behind the webinar was a community discussion of what they thought should be done next to implement or enhance the roadmap recommendations. In order to facilitate this discussion the design was based around a keynote presentation from a senior member of the project team, with responses from

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invited stakeholders representing groups with a keen interest in the development of the PID ecosystem, namely researchers, publishers and e-infrastructure providers.

ODIN Webinar

Sort: [Preset](#) / [Date](#) / [Alphabetical](#) / [Plays](#) / [Likes](#) / [Comments](#) / [Duration](#)

ODIN Webinar - Proof of concept: INSPIRE...
6 minutes ago

ODIN Webinar - DataCite Services - Sebast...
6 minutes ago

ODIN Webinar - ORCID member integration...
6 minutes ago

ODIN Webinar - Introduction - Josh Brown
6 minutes ago

Fig. 8: Videos of the presentations given during the first ODIN Webinar.

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The webinars were promoted via posts on the main project blog, supported with dedicated pages on the project site and via the project partners. They were also promoted via mailing lists and social media.

Printed Material

As noted in section 3.2, work has recently been completed to derive material based on the deliverables from Work Packages 3, 4 and 5. However, it is already clear that the findings of these work packages, and the accompanying Roadmap for future PID interoperation, will be of significant interest to the community of practitioners and researchers. The findings not only formed the basis of the September webinar and additional training guides, but were also used as material for the eight-page 'project findings' booklet (described in section 3.2 and shown in fig. 3). This was shared with delegates at the 4th Research Data Alliance (RDA) plenary in Amsterdam, September 22-24 2014, and at the co-located ODIN project final event, on September 24.

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Fig. 9: Flyer for the ODIN final event.

This used the same visual language as the training materials (see Fig. 2) already produced for the project, and in the ODIN final event flyer (see Fig. 9, and section 6.3). This booklet will also be distributed at other events after the life of the project by members of the team, to enhance post-project impact of the roadmap and other key outputs from the second year of the project.

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Impact of derived materials

The impact of many of the activities described in this chapter is amenable to tracking via web metrics, and indicates a very strong interest in the ODIN project and its outputs.

Fig. 10: Visitors to the ODIN project website over the life of the project.

Fig. 11: Graphs showing the number of unique visitors to the ODIN website, and the number of unique pages they viewed.

Examining the history of visits to the site (see Fig. 10), there have been clear increases in visits to the site around major project outreach activities. There are peaks around the ORCID Outreach Meeting, in May 2013; the project First Year Event, in October 2013; the launch of training materials in April and May 2014; the first ODIN project

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webinar in June 2014; and around the second webinar and the project final event in September 2014. Each visitor to the site tends to click through to additional pages, an average of two per visitor (see Fig. 11).

The codesprints generated considerable community interest, with participation across the three codesprints of 50 developers and a positive reaction from the community to the developed tools.

The first ODIN webinar attracted 177 registrants, 123 of whom attended the webinar itself. The Tweet from the ORCID official account promoting the webinar was extremely popular, and was viewed 851 times (see Fig.12). These videos have been viewed 250 times (see Fig. 13).

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YOU GOT SOME ATTENTION WITH THIS TWEET.

Webinar for developers working with ORCID, DataCite, and persistent IDs: [attendee.gotowebinar.com/register/37101....](http://attendee.gotowebinar.com/register/37101...)

06:58 AM - 29 May 14

851 views 3 favorites 10 link visits 10 Retweets

Great job this week!
Why not tweet about it?

Tweet

Fig. 12: Twitter statistics from ORCID official account, taken from a notification sent June 2, 2014.

Fig. 13: Play counts for videos of ODIN first webinar presentations, captured August 22 2014.

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The webinar and associated blog posts and videos drove a significant surge in traffic to the ODIN website (see Fig. 14). The first large spike in Figure 13 corresponds to the original announcement of the webinar. The second large spike corresponds to the webinar itself. These visitors also tended to spend more time exploring the website.

Fig. 14: Visits to the ODIN website around the first ODIN webinar, June 4 2014.

The second webinar attracted 87 registrants, of whom 54 joined the webinar on September 9th. The videos of the presentations have so far been viewed 53 times altogether (see fig. 15). This webinar, similarly to the first the project presented in June, drove a noticeable spike in traffic to the ODIN website (see fig. 16).

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Fig. 15: Play counts for videos of ODIN second webinar presentations, captured October 7 2014.

Fig. 16: Visits to the OSIN website around the second webinar, September 9 2014.

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Engagement with Existing and Emerging Initiatives

ODIN partners have been extremely active citizens in the data management community, and have covered many aspects of the issues around data management, from data publishing to handling research dataset metadata in current research information systems (CRISs).

Research Data Alliance (RDA)⁶

The RDA has been a valuable forum for ODIN to gather expertise from outside the project and to help to shape thinking about issues in research data. The RDA structures its activities as a mix of Interest Groups (for communities of practice or interest to discuss advances and issues in their field), and limited duration Working Groups (which aim to drive progress in specific areas of activity or community concern). The ODIN partners, collectively and as individual organisations, have emerged as a driving force within the RDA.

ORCID Co-founded the Persistent Identifier Interest Group with Adrian Burton (ANDS) and Tobias Weigel (DKRZ); this held its first meeting at the 3rd Plenary. ORCID is also a member of the Organizational Advisory Board. Laura Paglione (ORCID) participates on the Federated Identity Interest Group. ORCID and RDA have an MOU, which established ORCID as an affiliate member.

⁶ <https://rd-alliance.org/>

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Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen (CERN) and Elizabeth Newbold (BL) are, together with Theodora Bloom (BMJ), the co-chairs of the RDA working group for Data Publishing Workflows. The group comprises members from the publishing, e-infrastructure, library and research community. Its aim is a better understanding of modern data publishing workflows across disciplines, with the goal of enabling researchers, editors, publishers and any other interested person to identify successful data publishing models and re-use components of such models. The work and objectives of ODIN have been presented in this working group to elicit feedback on the disciplinary proofs of concepts and the workflows therein. In addition, these ODIN workflows have been exposed in a webinar (organized by the STM Association⁷) dedicated to data publishing.

Amir Aryani and Adrian Burton (ANDS) chair the Data Description Registry Interoperability Working Group. Sergio Ruiz (DataCite) is also taking part actively in this group. It aims to address the problem of cross-platform discovery through a series of bilateral information exchange projects and work toward open, extensible, and flexible cross-platform research data discovery software solutions.

Sergio Ruiz (DataCite) is also taking part in the RDA/WDS Publishing Data Interest Group, which brings together stakeholders involved in publishing research data including researchers, discipline specific and institutional data repositories, academic publishers, funders and service providers.

⁷ <http://www.stm-assoc.org/>

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Both British Library (Elizabeth Newbold and Rachael Kotarski) and DataCite (Sergio Ruiz) partners were invited to attend an RDA Data Citation Working Group meeting, which was also hosted at the British Library. The Data Citation WG is specifically tasked with investigating the citation of subsets of data. This workshop aimed to bring together practitioners to discuss improved ways of citing dynamic data, including changes over time. This was particularly relevant to the discussions with the MRC National Survey of Health and Development (MRC NSHD) on how to work identifiers for citation into their workflow, which is centred on data from a longitudinal study.

CASRAI⁸

ORCID has a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with CASRAI. When possible, ORCID metadata is compliant with CASRAI standards, and ORCID co-chaired and funded a CASRAI working group on developing metadata standards for citing peer review activities. Members of the ORCID team participated in CASRAI ReConnect meetings in Ottawa (2013), Rome (2014), and Washington DC (2014), promoting ODIN to this audience.

CHAIN-REDS⁹

CHAIN-REDS is a project aiming at promoting and supporting technological and scientific collaboration across different e-Infrastructures established and operated in various continents. Following a presentation delivered by Sergio Ruiz (DataCite) in December 2013 in a CHAIN-REDS workshop, DataCite has kept in contact with the

⁸ <http://casrai.org/>

⁹ <https://www.chain-project.eu/>

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project. Thanks to this relationship one of the CHAIN-REDS partners is now actively involved with the Italian DataCite member (CRUI).

EPIC¹⁰

EPIC is a European Consortium created to provide PID services for the European Research Community, based on the handle system for the allocation and resolution of persistent identifiers. EPIC PIDs are mainly intended for data reference and citability with EPIC PIDs possible, but DataCite PIDs (DOIs) have the branding for citability. In order to facilitate a seamless transition, EPIC has an agreement with DataCite and the German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB), one of DataCite members, by which a special DOI prefix is used. This way the EPIC PID (prefix/suffix) becomes suffix of this DOI prefix.

In 2013 The Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG) became a DataCite affiliated member on behalf of the EPIC consortium.

EuroCRIS¹¹

ORCID has a Memorandum of Understanding with EuroCRIS, the European body tasked with maintaining and developing the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF), a standard commonly used in CRISs. The ORCID team have worked with EuroCRIS on database field structures, and regularly participate in EuroCRIS international meetings. At the CRIS 2014 conference in Rome, delegates from ORCID

¹⁰ <http://www.pidconsortium.eu/>

¹¹ <http://www.eurocris.org>

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leveraged the numerous presentations and discussions of the challenges of integrating research datasets and associated metadata in CRISs to promote ODIN.

FIM4R

Laura Paglione (ORCID) participated in 2013 and 2014 FIM4R meetings and through that entered into conversations with TERENA¹² about how ORCID may contribute to federated identity management, as a component of the data exchanged during authorization. In discussions about a possible technical collaboration, FIM4R has become the RDA Federated Identity Interest Group.

Force11¹³

The RDA Data Publishing Workflow group has joint calls with Force11 to allow a global assessment of workflows, with a focus on the facilitation of data citation. This has been very fruitful and allowed for a wider dissemination of the ODIN objectives and outputs.

In May 2014, Force 11 published the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Several individuals linked to different ODIN partners participated actively in the production of those principles. The Data Citation Principles cover the purpose, function and attributes of citations. They recognize the dual necessity of creating citation practices that are both human understandable and machine-actionable. To date they have been endorsed by more than 250 individuals and organizations from all over the world.

¹² <http://www.terena.org/>

¹³ <https://www.force11.org/>

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FOSTER¹⁴

FOSTER, as a European network for Open Science training, is very interested in a better understanding of PIDs as an enabler for Open Science. There are plans to strengthen the collaboration to disseminate ODIN results in their training networks better, i.e. to teach the benefits of using PIDs to a wide range of stakeholders.

ISNI, Linked Data¹⁵

ORCID established a Memorandum of Understanding with ISNI for a coordinated approach to providing persistent identifiers for people. The ORCID registry uses ISNI Registration Agency (Ringgold) as source of organizational identifiers. As a crucial component of the ODIN interoperability framework, the team collaborated with ISNI to build and launch the ISNI2ORCID search and link tool. More details can be found in D4.2 (Workflow for interoperability).

OpenAIRE¹⁶

OpenAIRE aims to support the implementation of Open Access in Europe, by promoting the widespread adoption of the Open Access Policy set out in the guidelines published by the European Commission. The project is extending the mission further to facilitate access, providing cross-links from publications to data and funding schemes.

¹⁴ <http://www.fosteropenscience.eu/>

¹⁵ <http://www.isni.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

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OpenAIRE's Orphan Record Repository (branded as Zenodo¹⁷, and currently hosted at CERN) provides a service for articles and/or research data when the community lacks an institutional repository or a subject repository.

OpenAIRE and ODIN have been collaborating in the development of cross-linking technologies and proofs of concept. Zenodo and INSPIRE are now connected and share software preservation records extracted from GitHub, using standards like OAI-PMH.

Taking advantage of the underlying technology and using DOIs as persistent identifiers for data, INSPIRE provides added value services to Zenodo content such as citation tracking, publication cross-linking and author recognition.

Impact of engagement with existing and emerging initiatives

ODIN partners have been extremely active across the research data and PID landscape, with 19 members of the project team participating formally in 15 initiatives, and shaping the development of standards (such as EuroCRIS and CASRAI), best practice (such as the Force11 Data Citation Principles) and related technologies (such as Access Management). The project has also engaged with the implementation of core European policies, such as Open Access via OpenAIRE.

¹⁷ <http://zenodo.org/>

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The breadth of activities of ODIN members in the RDA merits a special mention here. ODIN partners participate in six groups within the RDA, a cluster of partnerships that has proved so receptive and fruitful that the decision was taken to co-locate the ODIN project event with the 4th RDA Plenary in Amsterdam. The audience at previous RDA plenaries has been extremely interested in ODIN outputs and work, and this was a key audience for the promotion of the deliverables, findings and events coming from the project.

Conferences and Publications

The ODIN project has generated an extensive list of conference papers and formal publications in addition to regular blog posts and other project outputs. The project has featured in 13 conference presentations and posters, six articles, and one conference panel discussion. All the partners have been heavily engaged with this activity, as can clearly be seen from the list of authors presented in the sections 5.1 and 5.2. One of the key purposes of this publication activity has been to draw important

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messages out of the formal project deliverables and to package them for specific audiences or interest groups.

The audience reached by these activities has been broad, from the information profession (Digital Libraries) and research managers (EuroCRIS, CASRAI) to disciplinary communities (Digital Humanities). The consistent feature of the audiences targeted has been that they all have some capacity to implement the products or findings of ODIN, and all have the capacity to both integrate and benefit from PID infrastructures.

Conference papers

Laurel Haak (ORCID). *ORCID & ODIN*. DataCite summer meeting 2013, September 19, 2013, Washington, USA. <http://river-valley.tv/conferences/datacite2013>

Laura Rueda et al. (CERN). *Providing Meaningful Information in a Large Scale Digital Library – a Case Study*. 17th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, September 22-26, 2013, Valletta, Malta. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-40501-3_28

Adrian Burton and Amir Aryani (ANDS). *ORCID integration: A case study from ANDS and international development*. eResearch Australasia 2013, October 22, 2013, Brisbane, Australia. <http://www.slideshare.net/amiraryani/ORCID-ands-integration-e-research-2013>

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Jan Brase (DataCite). *Neue Rollen für Bibliotheken: Das Beispiel DataCite*. Max Planck PubMan Days, October 24, 2013, Munich, Germany. <http://pubman-days.mpg.de/programm-2013/>

Sergio Ruiz (DataCite). *The ODIN Project: ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network*. CHAIN-REDS Workshop: e-Infrastructures for Education, Research & Development, December 11, 2013, Tunis, Tunisia. http://www.asrenorg.net/eage2013/sites/default/files/files/CHAIN-REDS_WSTunis_ag...

Sergio Ruiz (DataCite). *ODIN: Connecting research and researchers*. Citizen Cyberscience Summit 2014, February 21, 2014, London, UK. <http://lanyrd.com/2014/citizen-cyberscience-summit/sctyzk/>

Todd Vision (Dryad), John Kaye (British Library) and Amir Aryani (ANDS). *Towards identifier-aware cyberinfrastructure for data and researchers*. 9th International Digital Curation Conference, February 24-27, 2014, San Francisco, USA. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.907482>

John Kaye (British Library). *Using Identifiers to Connect Researchers with Research*. Digital Humanities Australasia 2014, March 17, 2014, Perth, Australia. http://figshare.com/articles/DHA_2014_ANDS_Workshop_ODIN_Presentation/963000

Laure Haak (ORCID), David Baker (CASRAI), Thorsten Hoellrigl (Thomson Reuters). *CASRAI and ORCID – Putting the pieces together to collaboratively support the*

	D2.4 Final communication report including results from final event		
	WP2 Communication		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: J.Brown (ORCID), S.Dallmeier-Tiessen, L. Rueda (CERN), R.Kotarski, S.Ruiz (BL), T.Vision (Dryad)	Version: 1_1 Final	45/59

Research Community. 12th International Conference on Current Research Information Systems, May 13-15, 2014, Rome, Italy. <http://www.cris2014.org/>

Elizabeth Newbold (BL). *Using identifiers to connect researchers, authors and contributors with their research data*. iAssist 2014, June 3-6, 2014, Toronto, Canada. <http://www.library.yorku.ca/cms/iassist/program/sb5/>

Tom Demeranville (BL). *Connecting you, your PhD and your published research: an ORCID ETHOS linking solution*. ETD 2014 – 17th International Symposium on Electronic Theses and Dissertations, July 23-25, 2014, Leicester, UK. <http://www2.le.ac.uk/library/etd2014/programme>

Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), Laura Paglione (ORCID). *DataCite and ORCID: Towards Holistic Open Research*. DataCite Annual Conference, August 25-26, 2014, Nancy, France. <http://datacite.inist.fr/>

Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Artemis Lavasa, Patricia Herterich, Laura Rueda (CERN), Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL). *A comparative analysis of the HSS & HEP data submission workflows within the ODIN project*. Digital Libraries 2014, September 08-12, 2014, London, UK

The ODIN Project has also been mentioned in different presentations to librarians, researchers, policy makers and funders such as:

- London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine. Library resources: making the most of the National Treasure. Month February 2014, London (UK).

	D2.4 Final communication report including results from final event		
	WP2 Communication		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: J.Brown (ORCID), S.Dallmeier-Tiessen, L. Rueda (CERN), R.Kotarski, S.Ruiz (BL), T.Vision (Dryad)	Version: 1_1 Final	46/59

- Economic and Social Research Council. Connecting researchers with research objects. Presentation delivered to the Methods and Infrastructures Committee. March 2013, London.
- Library of Congress. Social Sciences at the British Library. September 2013, Washington DC (USA).
- ESRC National Centre for Research Methods. Introduction to the British Library. June 2013, London (UK).
- Social Researchers Association. Social Research and the Social Media introduction. May 2014. London (UK).

Journal articles

Adam Farquhar and Jan Brase. *Data Identification and Citation — The Key to Unlocking the Promise of Data Sharing and Reuse*. D-Lib Magazine. Volume 20, Number 1/2 January/February.

<http://www.dlib.org/dlib/january14/farquhar/01farquhar.html>

Dr. Laure Haak. *CASRAI and ORCID: Putting the pieces together to collaboratively support the research community*. Procedia Computer Science (2014), pp. 284-288.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2014.06.045>

Martin Fenner, Gudmundur A. Thorisson, Sergio Ruiz, Jan Brase. *ODIN: The ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network*. International Journal of Knowledge and Learning (IJKL) Special issue: Towards Trusted Persistent Identifier Infrastructures. In press.

	D2.4 Final communication report including results from final event		
	WP2 Communication		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: J.Brown (ORCID), S.Dallmeier-Tiessen, L. Rueda (CERN), R.Kotarski, S.Ruiz (BL), T.Vision (Dryad)	Version: 1_1 Final	47/59

Michael Charno, Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Catherine Hardman, Patricia Herterich, Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold and Laura Rueda. *Integrating Persistent Identifiers for authors and data: two case studies*. D-Lib magazine. In press.

Additional articles are in preparation for submission to the CODATA Data Science Journal and Nature News and Comment.

Open Repositories 2014

In addition to these conference papers, the project team undertook extended outreach at the Open Repositories 2014 (OR14) conference in Helsinki. There were a number of representatives of the project partners present and active at the conference, including:

- arXiv: Simeon Warner
- Australian National Data Service: Amir Aryani
- CERN: Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen
- DataCite: Sebastian Peters
- Dryad Digital Repository: Ryan Scherle, Todd Vision
- ORCID: Laura Paglione, Rob Peters

The project co-sponsored the Developer Challenge at the conference, encouraging the developers who attended the event to both actively deploy PIDs in their entries in the challenge, and to understand the range of tools and services available to them in their day-to-day work running repositories. The aim was to promote the work done in the project directly to an active group of implementers working on live systems.

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	WP2 Communication		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: J.Brown (ORCID), S.Dallmeier-Tiessen, L. Rueda (CERN), R.Kotarski, S.Ruiz (BL), T.Vision (Dryad)	Version: 1_1 Final	48/59

The results of the challenge have been published on the OR14 website, and have been described in more detail in section 2.6. The project team who were present at the Developer Challenge reported strong interest in PIDs amongst the community present, and provided live demonstrations and tutorials of the APIs available from ORCID and DataCite.

The second strand in structured outreach at the conference was a panel discussion during the main conference programme.

Sunje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Laure Paglione, Sebastian Peters, Todd Vision. *Promoting Interoperability and Services through shared identifiers*. Open Repositories 2014, June 9-13, Helsinki, Finland.

http://www.conftool.com/or2014/index.php?page=browseSessions&form_session=101

The session offered a technical discussion of the use of PIDs as a support for interoperable research platforms and the services built on top of them. Laura Paglione (ORCID) and Sebastian Peters (DataCite) discussed implementation challenges for PID registries, including the need for community engagement and ongoing support for the development of third party services. Sunje Dallmeier-Tiessen (CERN) and Ryan Scherle (Dryad) explored the challenges and opportunities for integrating shared PIDs from the perspective of platform providers. The panel discussion was recorded, and is available via the summary page on the conference site.

Impact of conferences and publications

As noted above, the project team have participated extremely actively in writing and presenting synthesised project outputs. As well as four formal publications accepted

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for publication, and two further publications submitted for publication at the time of writing, the team has travelled extensively to promote the project outputs and findings to audiences across Europe and beyond. Figure 17 gives an overview of the scale and breadth of these activities.

Number of conference presentations	13
Number of international conferences	13
Number of continents covered	4
Total number of conference delegates	2,500*

*This represents a *conservative* estimate, as delegate numbers are not available for all conferences.

Fig. 17: Overview of ODIN partners' promotional conference activity

These presentations have reached a considerable audience of at least 2,500 people, drawn from professional fields including data centre staff; librarians; repository managers and developers; educationalists; research administrators and managers; software and systems vendors; standards bodies; publishers; and science policy-makers.

The disciplinary fields covered have extended beyond the core groups within High-Energy Physics and the Humanities and Social Sciences, to cross-disciplinary groups in Graduate Education and 'big science'.

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Audiences have characteristically been very engaged with presentations from the project team. As an example, the audience at the OR2014 panel discussion was described by the presenters as 'very lively', and discussions ranged from business models of ORCID and DataCite to naming conventions. Forty five tweets came from this event, linked specifically to ODIN, DataCite or ORCID.

Project Events

Project kickoff

The ODIN kickoff meeting took place October 18th, 2012 at the Kalkscheune in Berlin, leveraging a series of ORCID-sponsored events taking place during that week in Berlin. The full-day kickoff meeting included 11 presentations and the size and programme of the event provided the right format for many insightful discussions relevant for the ODIN project.

The meeting provided an overview of the current persistent identifier discussion, as well as valuable input from key stakeholders to the ODIN project. The eleven presenters (from a variety of stakeholder groups) provided important perspectives, and the extensive discussion by all meeting participants further elaborated on key points. Based on the key scientific inputs, the following actions were identified:

- further encouragement of discussion and collaboration between communities

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- need to address specific issues of working with large number of small heterogeneous datasets
- benefits of identifying main interoperability use cases and define their business value
- the importance of encouraging the development of novel tools to track the reuse of data.

The scientific input obtained during the kickoff meeting proved valuable in attaching a series of concrete actions to each of the main ODIN challenges that have been taken into account through the whole duration of the project.

First year event

One year after the ODIN launch, a major ODIN community event was held at the Globe Conference Centre, CERN, between October 15 and October 17 2013. This was a combination of a hands-on Codesprint (or Hackathon) and a more traditional Conference.

Codesprint

The Codesprint targeted the technical communities interested in building on the first year results of ODIN, in particular of the results of WP4. Their engagement resulted in several new features that were developed over the course of the 1.5 days event.

We engaged stakeholders beyond the technical community, i.e. representatives from data centres, libraries, publishers and a diverse set of disciplines. ODIN project members presented the first results to the attendees to get feedback on the applicability and transferability of these results to other communities. The diverse set

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of invited speakers provided additional insights into the different perspectives and experiences of the individual stakeholder groups, which proved very useful for the second period of the project.

The main purpose of the Codesprint was to provide a venue for both ODIN participants and external invited experts to work together on creating proof-of-principle software, which demonstrate the potential of the identifier “awareness layer”. The intention was to engage with stakeholders within and outside of ODIN and collaboratively explore capabilities, gaps and opportunities resulting from the emergent infrastructure.

It also served to stress test the proposed workflows and proofs of concept presented by the ODIN members. Positive feedback was received from the community, and the opportunity to validate approaches through the creation of hands-on applications was very valuable for the project members.

Conference

The First Year Conference lasted one full day, on October 17 2013. The first part of the programme comprised an update from DataCite and ORCID and a summary of the first results from the project. The majority of the programme, however, was devoted to presentations from external speakers representing a diverse group of stakeholder organizations. This provided the community with an opportunity to provide feedback on the ODIN project outputs from the first year, and to update the team and each other on specific challenges that they faced. This input was crucial to the evolution of the second year of the ODIN project.

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Full details for both the Codefest and the Conference can be found in D2.3 (First year communication report including results from first year event).

Final event

The ODIN Final Event took place in Amsterdam, on September 24 2014. It was a half-day event, to take advantage of the fact that the collocated RDA 4th plenary ended after morning sessions that day and the majority of this vital audience would therefore be able to participate, and was comprised of a mix of plenary and parallel sessions.

Presenters from the project team demonstrated project outputs in action at different stages of the research lifecycle, including data discovery and analysis, submission to a datacentre, and publication and citation. There were two breakout sessions, one a policy-led discussion exploring the barriers to, and drivers for, meaningful change in PID integrations, the other a technical demonstration of the tools developed during the project.

Keynote speakers for the event were Dr Merce Crosas, Director of Data Science at IQSS, Harvard University, who explored the context and challenges for data services and Dr Simon Hodson, Executive Director of CODATA, who offered an exploration of the implications of the ODIN roadmap for the global data community.

87 delegates registered to attend the event, and 82 attended (see picture 1, below). Discussion in the breakout sessions was extremely lively and engaged, and demonstrated the clear community appetite both for improved access to and uptake of PIDs and for immediate access to tools and services to enable them to take advantage of the project outputs.

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Picture 1: Standing room only at the ODIN Final Event.

Impact of events

While the primary intention of the project kickoff event was for it to shape and guide the development of the project, it also provided a valuable boost to the general awareness of the project at the outset, especially in key organisations operating in the field.

A total of 64 participants attended the first year event. The event generated 40 tweets and provided a forum for community feedback to the project team. This was clear evidence of a highly-engaged and well-informed community of interest around the project, a finding which has been reinforced by the levels of interest in subsequent communications activities, such as the project webinars and the panel discussion hosted at OR2014.

The first-year codesprint attracted 20 participants from a range of organisations. The projects were diverse in nature, ranging from building a set of tools that users can

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utilise to embed a list of their datasets and other ORCID-claimed works in their personal webpage, to analysing and cross-matching metadata content of ORCID and DataCite, in order to identify author-dataset links to push to a data centre. More details about each of these projects is given in section 3.3.

ODIN project events have generated substantive inputs to the evolution and development of the project, and we were pleased to be able to demonstrate how this shaped our work at the ODIN final event in September 2014. The size of the audience, 82, indicated clearly that this event was of keen interest to the community, and the quality of the discussion in breakout sessions gives an early indication that the final oputputs from the project have engaged community interest and will serve to stimulate an ongoing discussion.

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Concluding Remarks

Roxanne Persaud @commutiny · Dec 9

Check out odin-project.eu fascinating project exploring how individual researcher identifiers could be used - get ORCID! #SRAconf

RETWEETS

5

FAVORITES

3

2:12 AM - 9 Dec 2013 · Details

Collapse

↩ Reply
↻ Retweet
★ Favorite
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In the second year Communication Action Plan, a number of key goals and targets were set out. These were:

- Extend and strengthen ongoing collaborations with major stakeholders in scholarly communication.
- Present ODIN results at least at 6 international conferences with 100+ attendees.
- Organize final ODIN event attracting 70+ attendees.
- Organize extra technical workshop attracting ~30 attendees.
- Engage directly with key stakeholder groups.
- Publish at least 2 articles in peer-reviewed journals.
- Publish range of derived materials on the project website.
- Publish at least one blog post per month on the project website.

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This report demonstrates that each of these goals has been met or exceeded (the technical workshop, held as a webinar, drew 123 attendees, meaning that the expected target attendance was exceeded by a factor of four and there are four papers published or in press, with two further papers submitted).

While some activities continue, it is apparent that the ODIN communication strategy has delivered significant value and impact during the second year. As was to be expected, this impact gathered pace as we approached the end of the project, with the final deliverables, a fresh suite of training, guidance and synthesised project materials, a second webinar and the project final event all delivered during the last month of the project.

The balanced strategy employed by the project, to ensure that findings were communicated directly to stakeholder groups wherever possible has shaped priorities. The extremely high level of community activity evinced by the project members (chapter 4), taken alongside the extensive conference presentation and publication portfolio (chapter 5), demonstrates that one central activity of this project has been to share its findings and developments with all stakeholders. The growing level of interest and engagement with project outputs, and the increasing levels of interest in the project in wider communities of practice suggest that this approach has paid dividends, and will continue to do so.

While the final pattern of impact of the project is yet to be seen, the trend is positive, and with a substantial tranche of project deliverables, training materials, publications and outreach activity freshly completed and released, we anticipate that this impact will continue to grow both in the short-term and after the project has been completed.

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Appendix 1: Action PLAN STATUS

This table reviews the current status of the actions proposed in the Dissemination and Community Engagement Action Plan submitted in June 2014.

Communication action	Delivery	Status
Redesign the project website and use it more actively for publishing project outputs	April '14	Completed
Generation of dissemination material (training concepts, specifications, integration guidelines...) for stakeholders	August '14	Completed
Publication process and infrastructure checklists to assist new implementations of the 'thin layer'	September '14	Completed
Publication of parallel projects, codesprint results and scientific articles in the website and other dissemination efforts	September '14	Completed
Publication of blog posts, internal, guest blog posts in the ODIN website and guest blog posts in other sites	Throughout project	Completed

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Delivery of webinars for targeted training	June '14	Completed
	September '14	Completed
Printed material	September '14	Completed
Extend and strengthen ongoing collaborations between ODIN partners and other major stakeholders	September '14	Completed
Communication action	Delivery	Status
Present ODIN results at multiple suitable conferences both during the project and after its completion	August '14	Completed
Prepare articles regarding the results obtained by ODIN for international journals	September '14	Completed
Organise technical, development and infrastructure related event following the Codesprint ideas	June '14	Completed
Organise the final conference of the project	September '14	Completed

